

POLARIN

POLAR
RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURE
NETWORK

Guidelines for uploading research outputs to OpenAIRE
and the use of POLARIN Zenodo Community

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SUMMARY

This document provides practical guidelines for the use of Zenodo within the POLARIN project. It explains how Zenodo is used to manage and publish selected project documents and datasets and describes the step-by-step procedure for publishing in the POLARIN Zenodo community. The document clarifies roles, responsibilities, and governance, including required checks to ensure compliance with Horizon Europe, Open Science, and data management requirements. It specifies the key steps and conditions that must be fulfilled to guarantee that publications meet project and EC standards.

1. Introduction

The POLARIN project is an international network of polar research infrastructures and services, operating under the Horizon Europe program within the Research Infrastructures cluster (HORIZON.1.3). POLARIN aims to address scientific challenges in polar regions by providing integrated, challenge-driven access to a diverse array of top-level research infrastructures, including Arctic and Antarctic research stations, research vessels, observatories, and data centers. This initiative seeks to enhance data availability and interoperability, thereby improving access to polar data and facilitating interdisciplinary research on complex processes.

An open and free data policy is highly promoted by the European Commission and its member states for a wide range of environmental data services targeted to a wide range of user communities. To achieve its objectives, POLARIN aligns with several European frameworks and principles:

1. CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service): as the European Commission's primary portal for disseminating information about EU-funded research projects, CORDIS ensures that project results are accessible and traceable. Information about POLARIN is available on CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130949>), ensuring transparency and facilitating knowledge transfer within the scientific community and beyond.
2. OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe): this initiative supports the implementation of open science policies in Europe by providing open-access repositories and data-sharing infrastructures. By making project contributions accessible through repositories supported by OpenAIRE, e.g., Zenodo, facilitates compliance with EU open science mandates and promotes data sharing and reuse among researchers and policymakers.
3. FAIR Principles¹ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable): these guidelines advocate for the proper management of research data to ensure long-term accessibility and reusability. POLARIN adheres to the FAIR principles by implementing standardized data management practices, enhancing the discoverability and usability of polar data for the scientific community and other stakeholders.

2. What is Zenodo?

Zenodo is an open-access repository developed by CERN and supported by OpenAIRE, designed to host scientific publications, datasets, and other research outputs. It enables researchers to deposit materials in compliance with open-access standards, assigning DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for proper citation and indexing.

Key feature of Zenodo:

- Retriavibility: automatic DOI assignment, ensuring traceability and proper citation of uploaded materials.
- Storage of publications and datasets, allowing files up to 50GB per item (or up to 200GB in some cases, with approval).
- Support for open licensing (e.g., CC-BY), in line with EU open-access policies.
- Integration with OpenAIRE, facilitating compliance with Horizon Europe dissemination requirements.
- Long-term accessibility, ensuring that project outputs remain available beyond the project's duration.

¹<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

3. Use of Zenodo in POLARIN

A dedicated Zenodo community has been established for POLARIN materials (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-polarin/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>). Zenodo will be used in POLARIN to manage and publish specific documents and datasets, in details:

1. **Managing official project documents**, primarily deliverables, after they are approved by the EC reviewers. The publication of any document must be approved by the project's Steering Committee.
2. **Archiving selected datasets**: as POLARIN is a Horizon Europe project within the Research Infrastructures domain, its Zenodo community is included among the *Open repositories for EU-funded research*, with a storage allowance of up to 200GB per item. However, dataset publication is controlled by the POLARIN Data Manager to ensure completeness and validity and is aligned with the follow-up and implementation of the TA Data Management Plans.

If an embargo is required to protect data prior to publication, care should be taken not to disclose sensitive or premature information in related publications. Data can be uploaded to Zenodo under embargo, specifying a clearly defined embargo period. The embargo must be time-limited and must not extend beyond the end of the POLARIN project, as all POLARIN data are required to be publicly available by then.

Zenodo will not be used for:

- Peer-reviewed articles, since it could be cause of conflict with others publishers
- Confidential deliverables which are for the consortium access only
- Milestones (possibility to publish them only if the authors allow it)
- Project periodic reports to European Commission (once approved by the reviewers, they will be publicly available). They will be automatically added by the EC to the POLARIN project webpage on Cordis (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130949>).

In addition to Zenodo, other OpenAIRE-compatible platforms could have been considered depending on the type of data (e.g., PANGAEA for environmental and geoscientific data, SEANOE for oceanographic data, Figshare for various types of publications and datasets, and others...).

However, Zenodo is particularly suitable for POLARIN due to its seamless integration with OpenAIRE and the extended storage capacity granted to the project as a Horizon Europe initiative.

4. How do you upload contents into Zenodo?

1. Log in / Register to Zenodo: <https://www.zenodo.org/login/?next=%2Fdeposit>
2. Select “New Upload” from the dashboard (Figure 1) or directly from the POLARIN community (Figure 2): <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu->

[polarin/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest](https://polarin.records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest) (it is not mandatory to start the upload directly within the community, but it is essential to assign it before publishing the record).

Figure 1. New upload from the dashboard

Figure 2. New upload from POLARIN community

3. If you made a new upload from your dashboard, make sure to select the **POLARIN community** (Figure 3) before uploading the file.

Figure 3. Select the POLARIN community

In the **Files** section, either drag and drop your files or click *Upload files*, then press *Start upload* to begin the process (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Upload files

4. In the **Basic Information section**, make sure you complete all the mandatory fields (*):
 - a. Digital Object Identifier (DOI) (Figure 5): If you already have a DOI, select YES and write it. If you do not have one, ZENODO will automatically assign a DOI to your research output. This is critical for ensuring your work is uniquely identifiable and interoperable within the OpenAIRE ecosystem. Ensuring that your information remains up to date allows others to access and use the latest version of your research outputs.

Digital Object Identifier *

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

A DOI allows your upload to be easily and unambiguously cited. Example: 10.1234/foo.bar

Figure 5. DOI

- b. **Resource Type** (Figure 6): select the categories that best matches the content you are uploading:

Figure 6. Resource type

- c. **Title** (Figure 7): Ensure that it is clear, concise, and accurately describes the content.

Figure 7. Insert title

- d. **Publication date** (Figure 8)

Publication date

2024-11-05

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Figure 8. Publication date

- e. **Creators** (Figure 9): If you do not have an ORCID id, please register for one at <https://orcid.org>. Ensure that all author names and institutional affiliations are correctly formatted.

Creators

+ Add creator

Add creator

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name

Family name

Given names

Given names

Identifiers

e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations

Search or create affiliation

Role

Select role

✕ Cancel

✓ Save and add another

✓ Save

Figure 9. Add creators

- f. **Description** (Figure 10): Insert the abstract here. Ensure it is clear, concise, and accurately describes the content.

Description

Paragraph **B** *I*

+ Add description

Figure 10. Insert description

- g. **Licenses** (Figure 11): Select an Open Access license (e.g., CC-BY, CC0). Zenodo is OpenAIRE-compliant by default, but choosing the right license ensures your content is widely accessible.

Licenses

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
 The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. [Read more](#)

Edit Remove

+ Add standard + Add custom

Figure 11. Insert license

5. Under the **Recommended Information** section, complete with the following information:
 - a. **Contributors** (Figure 12): If you do not have an ORCID ID, please register one here <https://orcid.org>. Ensure that all author names and institutional affiliations are correctly formatted. This ensures proper attribution of the work in OpenAIRE.

Add contributor

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name Given names

Identifiers

Affiliations

Role ^{*}

✕ Cancel ✓ Save and add another ✓ Save

Figure 12. Add contributors

- b. **Keywords** (Figure 13): Use controlled vocabularies or standardized terms for subject categories (e.g., keywords from recognized scientific thesauri as [Global Change Master Directory](#)). This helps harmonize your data across repositories and increases compatibility with OpenAIRE's indexing system.

Keywords and subjects

ocean

(EuroSciVoc) Oceanography

(EuroSciVoc) Physical oceanography

(EuroSciVoc) Ocean chemistry

(EuroSciVoc) Ocean engineering

Figure 13. Add keywords

- c. **Dates** (Figure 14): use this field to update the date of submission, update and other relevant temporal information regarding your research output.

Dates

Date *	Type *	Description
YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/Y		

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

Figure 14. Insert the date of submission

- d. **Version** (Figure 15): Since 2017, Zenodo offers DOI versioning, allowing you to create a new DOI for each version of your research output. This makes it easier for users to cite the latest version of your work in their publications.

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Figure 15. Add last version

6. **Funding: Establish a link between your record and the POLARIN grant agreement number.**
If you forget these last steps, your record will not appear under POLARIN Community and it will not be harvested by the European Commission databases.

Under **Funding section** (Figure 16): Since Zenodo's mission is to collect EC-funded data, the repository provides a way to look up Grant Information. In Zenodo, you must manually add the awards or grants funding your research. For POLARIN, search for the project by entering the Grant Agreement number: **101130949** in the search field.

Awards/Grants

+ Add + Add custom

Figure 16. Add POLARIN Grant Agreement number

7. Under **Related works section** (Figure 17): if your publication is linked to other resources (e.g., datasets, software, or supplementary materials), ensure they are properly linked using the related identifiers feature (e.g., DOI). This helps OpenAIRE trace all related outputs from your project. Moreover, it not only provides context for your data but also makes it easier for others to cite your work in their publications.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
Select relation...			

+ Add related work

Figure 17. Add other resources linked to the publication

5. IMPORTANT: Establish a link between your record, POLARIN community and Grant Agreement number

If you forget these last steps, your record will not appear under POLARIN and it will not be harvested by the European Commission databases.

TWO necessary steps here:

- 1) If you make a **new upload** from the dashboard, be sure to type “**POLARIN**” (one word) at the top of the page and select the suggested item from the menu (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Select the POLARIN community

- 2) At the very bottom of the page, under “Funding”, type the grant agreement number **101130949** or type “**POLARIN**” in the field circled below (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Add other resources linked to the publication

6. If you uploaded a record but forgot to add it to the POLARIN community

Please follow these instructions:

<https://help.zenodo.org/docs/share/submit-to-community/>

Go to the record you want to submit to a community and click the cog-wheel icon to open the communities' menu.

Click **Submit to the community** in the dropdown menu.

Find the community you want to submit to and click the **Select** button.

Confirm you want to submit the record to the community by:

- Ticking the checkbox that allows curators to gain view and edit access to your record.
- Optionally, write a message to the curators.

Finally, click the blue **Submit to community** button.

7. How to monitor interoperability status

1. You can monitor your publication's interoperability status through the [OpenAIRE explore feature](#) (Figure 20). ZENODO automatically sends metadata to OpenAIRE, but you can check if your publication has been indexed correctly. In order to find out if your research outputs have been correctly indexed into OpenAIRE, **Search for POLARIN Grant Agreement number: 101130949**
- 2.

Advanced search

101130949

RESEARCH PRODUCTS (0) **PROJECTS (1)** DATA SOURCES (0) ORGANIZATIONS (0)

Filters 1 Projects for 101130949

Funder

- European Commission (1)

Start Year

- 2024 (1)

End Year

- 2029 (1)

POLARIN (POLARIN: POLAR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK)

Open Access Mandate for Publications and Research data · Project · 2024 - 2029 · Partners: Aurora College, CSIC, Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres, University of Turku, Lund University · +48 partners

Funder: European Commission Project Code: 101130949

Overall Budget: 14,588,100 EUR Funder Contribution: 14,588,100 EUR

The polar regions play a key role in the Earth's system. They are essential for our climate and are sentinels of climate change, human expansion, and the hunt of new resources. The polar regions are losing ice, and their oceans and land are changing rapidly. The...

Link to Share Deposit Embed

HELP

3.

4. *Figure 20. OpenAIRE explore*

8. Guidelines for requesting a Zenodo storage quota increase (up to 200 GB)

Since POLARIN is a Horizon Europe project, you may request an increase in the upload limit on Zenodo from the default **50 GB** to **200 GB** per record (note: the maximum number of files per record remains 100).

Steps to request a quota Increase

1. **Sign in to Zenodo:** log in to your Zenodo account at <https://zenodo.org>.
2. **Create a new record:** start a new deposit and fill in all relevant metadata. You do **not** need to upload the large file yet. Make sure to:
 - a. fill in the **title, description, and authors** (including affiliations)
 - b. select a **license**
 - c. specify the **funding information**, including the **Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe grant number**
3. **Save the record as a draft:** once you've entered the metadata, save the record without publishing it.
4. **Contact Zenodo support** via [Zenodo Contact Form](#) or email: zenodo@cern.ch

In your message, include:

- the **URL of the draft record**
- the reason for your request (i.e., you're part of an EC-funded project)
- your **grant number (101130949)** and the **name of the project (POLARIN)**
- **Wait for approval** Zenodo's support team will review your request. If approved, your record's quota will be increased, allowing you to upload up to 200 GB.

For a detailed walkthrough with visuals, consult the [Zenodo Help Documentation Quota Increase](#).

Issues?

If you have any issue with Zenodo, please contact Antonio Novellino and Rachele Bordoni (WP4).

If you wish to delete a record at any time, WP4 can help you but is not able to delete the records, for this we need to ask the intervention of the Zenodo staff.

Antonio Novellino, ETT S.p.A., antonio.novellino@dedagroup.it

Rachele Bordoni, ETT S.p.A, rachele.bordoni@outlook.it

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